

Studies on Some Soluble Palladium(II) Chelates in Aqueous Solution. Part I. Spectrophotometric Investigations of Palladium(II) - sulphodichlorohydroxydimethylfuchson Dicarboxylic Acid (Trisodium Salt) (Chrome Azurol S)

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Palladium(II) with Chrome Azurol S forms a 1:1 violet-coloured chelate (λ_{max} 585 m μ). The chelate is stable between pH 3.5 and 8.0. The values of stability constant ($\log K$) as determined by two different methods are 5.0 and 4.8 respectively at pH 4.0 (at 25°).

Most of the organic reagents used in the determination of palladium(II) are precipitants and not many compounds have been reported in literature which form soluble coloured chelates with palladium(II). Mention may, however, be made of the reagents: 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 2-nitroso-1-naphthol¹, α -furyl dioxime², bismuthiolI³, and 1-nitroso-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid⁴, which show colour reactions and have been employed for the colorimetric determination of palladium(II). During our studies with metal chelates of sulphodichlorohydroxydimethylfuchson dicarboxylic acid, we observed that palladium(II) produced a violet colour with the reagent. This communication records our results on the composition and stability of the chelate.

EXPERIMENTAL

Solutions of palladium chloride were prepared by dissolving a Johnson and Matthey sample in double distilled, CO-free water and standardised gravimetrically with dimethyl glyoxime. Solutions of different concentrations were prepared by suitable dilution.

Solutions of Chrome Azurol S (B. D. H. indicator, trisodium salt, colour index 723) were prepared in double distilled CO-free water. All other reagents were of the reagent grade. Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer with matched glass cells (1 cm) was used for absorptiometric measurements. pH measurements were done with a Leeds and Northrup direct reading pH indicator, using glass and calomel electrodes.

Composition of the Chelate.—Three different methods, viz. (i) Job's method of continued variation⁵, (ii) the mole-ratio method⁶, and (iii) the slope-ratio method⁷ were employed to establish the composition of the chelate.

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Evaluation of the Stability Constant.—Stability constants were determined using the method of Banerji and Dey⁸ and the mole-ratio method⁶.

Effect of Time on the Colour of the Chelate.—The colour of the chelate was formed immediately and the absorbance values did not change at least up to 72 hours. All the mixtures were, however, kept for an hour to attain equilibrium.

Nature of the Complexes Formed.—Mixtures containing 1:0, 1:0.5, 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, and 1:4 ratios of Chromo Azurol S to palladium were prepared, keeping the total volume 50 ml in each case and their absorbances measured. The results show that the maximum absorbance of the reagent lies at 485 m μ , whereas that of the mixtures at 585 m μ . This indicates that there is only one chelate with a $\lambda_{\max}$ 585 m μ under the conditions of study⁹.

Stoichiometry of the Components.—Table I records the summary of the results on the composition of the chelate, using Job's method (c represents the concentration of palladium chloride, and p is the ratio c'/c , c' being the concentration of Chrome Azurol S). A few observations are graphically recorded in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1. Composition by Job's method at 585 m μ ($p = 1$, pH 4.0).
Curve A: $c = 1.66 \times 10^{-4} M$.
Curve B: $c = 1.25 \times 10^{-4} M$.
Curve C: $c = 0.83 \times 10^{-4} M$.

FIG. 2. Composition by slope-ratio method (pH 4.0).
 $A, A' = 585$ m μ .
 $B, B' = 600$ m μ .
20 ml of $2.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ excess component + x ml of $0.83 \times 10^{-4} M$ variable component + $(30-x)$ ml of H_2O .

The composition of the chelate is thus indicated to be Pd(CAS) which is further supported by the results of the slope-ratio method (Fig. 2) and mole-ratio method (Fig. 3).

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TABLE I
 Total volume=25 ml.

Exp.	Curve No.	$c \times 10^4$.	p .	λ .	Vol. of PdCl ₂ at peak.	Composition of the chelate Pd: CAS.
I (Fig. 1)	A	1.66M	1.00	585m μ	12.50 ml	1 : 1
	B	1.25	1.00	585	12.50	1 : 1
	C	0.83	1.00	585	12.50	1 : 1
*Ia	A	1.66	1.00	600	12.50	1 : 1
	B	1.25	1.00	600	12.50	1 : 1
	C	0.83	1.00	600	12.50	1 : 1
*Ib	A	1.25	0.67	585	10.00	1 : 1
	B	0.83	1.50	585	15.00	1 : 1
*Ic	A	1.25	0.67	600	10.00	1 : 1
	B	0.83	1.50	600	15.00	1 : 1

*Figures omitted to economise space.

Effect of H⁺ ion Concentration on the Stability of the Chelate. The $\lambda_{\max}$ of the chelate (585 m μ) remains constant between pH 3.5 and 8.0. The maximum extinction lies at pH 4.0.

Calculation of the Stability Constant (K).—Table II shows the values of log K as determined by two different methods (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Composition by the mole-ratio method at 585 m μ (pH 4.0).

A: CAS=1.0 $\times 10^{-4}$ M.
 B: CAS=0.67 $\times 10^{-4}$ M.

TABLE II

Method.	pH.	log K.	ΔG° at 25°.
Method of Banerji and Dey ⁸	4.0	5.0 ± 0.2	-7.0 ± 0.2
Mole-ratio method	4.0	4.8 ± 0.1	-6.6 ± 0.1

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